

NOTES

Monoiodo Derivatives of Ni(III) and Co(III) Chelates with Some Schiff Bases

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NUMEROUS transition metal complexes of Schiff bases have been reported¹⁻⁷. In this communication, preparation and characterisation of monoiodo derivatives of Ni(III) and Co(III) chelates with four Schiff bases (H_2L) derived from 2-OH-5-Me aceto/propiofenone and ethylenediamine and 2-OH-5-Cl aceto/propiofenone ethylenediamine is described. The analytical data show them to have 1 : 1 : 1 composition of M : L : I.

Experimental

The four ligands were prepared by literature^{4,5} method by condensing the ketones, 2-OH-5-Me/Cl aceto/propiofenone with ethylenediamine in alcohol for about 1 hr. They were precipitated by pouring on ice. The precipitates were filtered, dried and recrystallised from chloroform.

Preparation of the complexes :

Equimolar quantities of nickel nitrate or cobaltous chloride (A.R. grade) in water were refluxed with the ligand in dioxane in the presence of acetate buffer (pH 6.5) for about 1 hr. The orange-red precipitates of Ni(II) or Co(II) complexes with the Schiff bases which separated on cooling were filtered. They were washed with distilled water and

then with alcohol to remove the excess metal and the ligand, respectively. The complexes were dried in vacuum at room temperature.

The metal-ligand complex and iodine in $CHCl_3/CCl_4$ were taken in 1 : 3 mole ratio and the mixture was refluxed for ~3 hr on a water bath. The brownish black precipitate which formed in hot was filtered after cooling and washed with CCl_4 to remove excess iodine. Later, 5% aqueous KI solution was also used to extract any left over iodine. An unusual observation was made during washing. Every time CCl_4 or KI solution was used to remove excess iodine from the complex, only some iodine came out into solution. Further addition of the solvent again extracted another small portion of I_2 . This went on for about 2 months. Only a definite fraction of I_2 seemed to dissolve at one time even on keeping the iodo-complex suspended in CCl_4 or KI solution for a week. It is only after a hundred or so washings spread over about 2 months, that the iodine stopped dissolving out from the solid complex. This residual complex was then analysed and found to be a monoiodo-complex. How the excess iodine was present in the complex and why it took so long to leach out in CCl_4 or KI solution is not understood.

All the monoiodo derivatives are soluble in dioxane and DMF, are partially soluble in acetone and are insoluble in all other organic solvents. The complexes were extracted with acetone using soxhlet-extraction method. Elemental analysis was done by standard methods⁸. Molecular weights were determined by Rast's camphor method. The data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Chelate	Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				Conductivity mhos $cm^2/mole$	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Metal	Iodine	Chlorine	Nitrogen		
1.	N,N' -ethylene bis(2-OH-5-Me aceto)Ni(III)I	520.3 (507.71)	11.45 (11.56)	25.1 (25.01)		5.45 (5.51)	9	1.79
2.	N,N' -ethylene bis(2-OH-5-Me propio)Ni(III)I	522.5 (535.71)	10.65 (10.7)	23.66 (23.70)		5.25 (5.22)	7	1.81
3.	N,N' -ethylene bis(2-OH-5-Cl aceto)Ni(II)I	560.5 (548.71)	10.89 (10.96)	23.09 (23.14)	6.56 (6.51)	5.14 (5.10)	7.8	1.78
4.	N,N' -ethylene bis(2-OH-5-Cl propio)Ni(III)I	565.8 (576.71)	9.99 (10.18)	22.06 (22.02)	6.09 (6.15)	4.9 (4.85)	9.2	1.81
5.	N,N' -ethylene bis(2-OH-5-Me aceto)Co(III)I	520.5 (507.9)	11.56 (11.59)	24.90 (25.00)		5.52 (5.51)	7	0.5
6.	N,N' -ethylene bis(2-OH-5-Me propio)Co(III)I	515.7 (535.9)	11.02 (10.99)	23.61 (23.69)		5.20 (5.22)	8	0.52
7.	N,N' -ethylene bis(2-OH-5-Cl aceto)Co(III)I	528.2 (548.9)	10.69 (10.73)	23.18 (23.13)	6.39 (6.46)	5.03 (5.10)	7.5	0.55
8.	N,N' -ethylene bis(2-OH-5-Cl propio)Co(III)I	590.5 (576.9)	10.17 (10.20)	22.05 (22.01)	6.17 (6.15)	4.7 (4.85)	7.2	0.5

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis showed that the complexes have a ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 giving MLI (M=Ni or Co) composition. The formula suggested that the moniodo complexes formed contained metal ions in the 3+ oxidation state and were presumably five-coordinate.

The molecular weights show that the complexes are monomeric. Thus the Schiff bases behave as tetradentate dibasic ligands as is known. The iodine seems to occupy the fifth coordination site giving five-coordinate Ni(III) and Co(III) complexes. The low conductivity of all the complexes in acetone confirms the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The room temperature magnetic moments (Guoy method, $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant, corrected for diamagnetism) of all Ni(III) complexes are 1.78-1.81 B.M. values close to the spin-only moment for one unpaired electron. Such values are known⁹ for Ni(III) complexes. The result is such as might be expected for the spin-paired configuration $b_{2g}^2 e^4 a_{1g}^1$. The room temperature magnetic moments of all the Co(III) complexes are found to be in the 0.5-0.6 B.M. range. This seems to be due to T.I.P.^{10,11}.

The ir spectra of the complexes showed the absence of the OH stretching band at $\sim 3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed in the ligands suggesting its deprotonation for the purpose of complex formation. The M-O stretching band is observed at $\sim 440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{12,13}. A band at $\sim 515 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{12,13} is considered to be due to M-N bond. The bands at 1620 cm^{-1} found in the ligands are found at $1580-1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹⁴ in the complexes, thereby suggesting the C=N group participation in coordination to the metal atom. A clear band in the far ir at $189-192 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹⁵ in these complexes is assigned to M-I stretching vibration.

Thus the complexes are apparently five-coordinate and presumably square-pyramidal, with one iodide out of plane of the rest of the molecule, and may be considered to have C_{4v} symmetry so that Ni(III) complex has 2A_1 and the Co(III) 1A_1 ground states.

The electronic spectra of the Ni(III) complexes in acetone exhibit bands around 400 and 505 nm which are also present in the ligands. Three more ill-defined weak bands are also observed around 560 ($\epsilon=240$), 680 ($\epsilon=86.80$) and 830 nm ($\epsilon=60$) in all Ni(II) complexes. The last two bands may be assigned to ${}^2A_1 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2A_1 \rightarrow {}^2E$ transitions. The band at 560 nm seems to be a charge transfer one.

The electronic spectra of the Co(III) complexes in acetone exhibit the intra-ligand bands around 400 and 505 nm. Three other bands are obtained at 630 ($\epsilon=420$), 685 ($\epsilon=265$) and 830 nm ($\epsilon=88$) in all the complexes which could be assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$; d_{yz} , $d_{xz} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$; d_{xz} , $d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions.

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Polarographic Determination of Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of the Complexes of Praseodymium(III) with Hydroxylamine, Hydrazine and Phenylhydrazine

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IN continuation of our previous work on the complexation study of cerium(III)¹ and neodymium(III)² with hydroxylamine, hydrazine and phenylhydrazine the present study on the complexes of praseodymium(III) with the same ligands is reported.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used to prepare all the solutions. The solutions of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, hydrazine hydrochloride and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (Chroma, Germany) were